

Evidence-based management of EIB with vitamin C

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This comment was originally published in BMJ, Rapid Response, 2016 February 29:

<https://www.bmj.com/content/352/bmj.h6951/rr>

The address of this version is: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20157560>

Comment on:

Smoliga JM, Weiss P, Rundell KW.

Exercise induced bronchoconstriction in adults: evidence based diagnosis and management.

BMJ. 2016 Jan 13;352:h6951.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26762594>

<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.h6951>

Smoliga, Weiss and Rundell reviewed exercise-induced bronchoconstriction (EIB) and implied in their title that they covered evidence-based managements of EIB.

EBM requires that the literature searches should be thorough, and RCTs and systematic reviews should be the primary focus of the searches. There are 3 RCTs on vitamin C and EIB and the pooled relative effect estimate indicates a 48% reduction (95% CI 33% to 64%) in the postexercise FEV₁ decline when vitamin C was administered before exercise [1,2]. These findings were not mentioned by Smoliga et al.

A subcommittee of the American Thoracic Society wrote guidelines about EIB and in the guidelines mentioned 2 RCTs about vitamin C [3]. I pointed out that a third RCT had been ignored in the guidelines, and I also pointed out that the statistical analysis of the 2 included RCTs was superficial, eg 95% CIs were not calculated [4]. Rundell was an author of the guidelines [3] and thus knew that there are RCTs on vitamin C and EIB.

Dismissing the evidence about vitamin C for EIB may be explained by the bias in mainstream medicine against treatments that do not need prescriptions [5,6].

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

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